

Statistical and Scientific Considerations for Bayesian Modelling of Vaccines Stability Studies

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Abstract

Long-term stability studies are conducted to establish a shelf-life of a drug substance or drug product for purposes of product licensure. We study the stability properties of a vaccine product. Ordinarily a simple linear model would be used to characterize the stability profile over time. Since vaccines do not always conform to a simple linear process, we propose a Bayesian mixed model framework that adjusts for specific departures from linearity. Two simple adjustments accounting for specific features of the vaccine product's stability profile were added to the model. The first adjustment is a simple quadratic term to account for curvature, balancing the desire for kinetic understanding with the need to meet the descriptive requirements of the data. The second adjustment relies on indicator variables to produce a segmented regression model to account for the change in potency during the early storage phase. The model showed good fit to the data and permitted a direct calculation of shelf life.

Key Words: Vaccines, long-term stability studies, shelf-life estimation, zero-order kinetic process, Bayesian approach, mixed model framework.

1. Introduction

The main aim of long-term stability studies is to find the shelf-life of a drug substance or drug product for purposes of product licensure. ICH guideline Q1E, *Evaluation of stability data*, recommends that for quantitative attributes, proper statistical methods may be employed where applicable. A main feature of the statistical analysis commonly used in stability studies for small molecule APIs is the close relationship to a zero-order kinetic process. However, special consideration is needed for vaccines and other products with unique stability characteristics as noted by Schofield (2009). For instance, some vaccines have special biochemical and physical characteristics which require a special protective form of packaging (vials), storage under very low frozen temperatures instead of room temperature and may have multiple degradation mechanisms whose modelling may not be well captured by a simple linear regression commonly applied in small molecule APIs.

In this paper, we focus on an example of a vector-based vaccine drug product observed to have changes in the monitored critical quality attribute (potency) during the early phase of its storage followed by stabilization in the later phase. We propose two simple adjustments to the linear stability model. The first adjustment is adding a simple quadratic term to account for curvature, balancing the desire for kinetic understanding with the need to meet the descriptive requirements of the data. The second adjustment proposes a segmented regression model to account for the change in potency during the early storage phase. A Bayesian approach in a mixed model framework is used for the analysis methodology.

Another important aim is to demonstrate the incorporation of scientific information in modelling stability data to ensure the most reliable estimation of vaccine shelf-life.

2. Data description

Study design: Several batches of a vaccine product were placed on stability under storage conditions (temperature) -60°C , -20°C , 5°C , and 25°C . The study for 5°C has two arms where vials are stored either in an upright or inverted orientation. Therefore, in total five storage conditions are studied. For each batch, the studies for the five storage conditions are started at the same time meaning that potency assay measurements at the start of the study (time zero) are common to all five storage conditions per batch. Further, for each batch, at each stability time point per storage condition, 9 assay measurements are taken from 3 independent assay runs (one vial per run) with each run having three independent replicate measurements from the same vial. The database comprised of a total of 21 batches. Random vials from each batch were placed in temperature-controlled stability chambers. Vials held at conditions -60°C , -20°C were assayed at intervals of 3 months until 12 months and every 6 months thereafter. Vials held at 5°C inverted and upright orientation were assayed at intervals of 1.5 months until the 9th month and every 3 months thereafter. Vials held at 25°C were assayed at intervals of 1.5 months until 6 months and no further assays were performed. An illustration of the data from the study for a single batch up to 12 months is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Scatter plot of stability data obtained from the study design described above for a single batch. The study for the five temperature conditions started at the same time. Therefore, data for each batch at the start (time zero) is common for all five conditions. There are 9 assay measurements at each time-point from 3 assay runs with 3 replicates per run.

Scientific input: In addition to the study design described above, we desire to incorporate the following scientific input into the statistical model.

- The change in potency over time for conditions -60°C , -20°C and 5°C upright vial orientation is hypothesised to have one-state kinetics (linear slope only).
- For storage condition 5°C inverted vial orientation, the change in potency over time is expected to follow two state kinetics a) an initial drop in potency immediately after time

zero which is associated with adsorption of the drug product to the extra unfilled glass surface area and the vial stopper after inversion and b) normal loss due to exposure to 5°C temperature which is expected to follow a simple linear relationship over time.

Finally, for condition 25°C, potency loss over time is expected to follow a nonlinear (quadratic) relationship.

3. Statistical model

Model formulation: Let $y_{m(ijkl)}$ denote an assay measurement (potency) from the study whose design is described above at time T_{ijk} with i, j, k, l, m denoting the batch, condition, time (in months), assay run and replicate respectively. Data obtained from the study design above accommodating scientific input relating to the expected stability behavior can be described with a mixed effects model as follows:

$$y_{m(ijkl)} = (A + \alpha_i) + (D_j + d_{ij}) \times Ind_{5C-Inv} * Ind_{1.5} + (\beta_j + b_{ij}) \times T_{ijk} + (W + \omega_i) \times Ind_{25C-up} \times T_{ijk}^2 + \gamma_{l(ik)} + \varepsilon_{m(ijkl)}$$

The terms in the mixed model are defined below.

- $y_{m(ijkl)}$ = Assay measurement at time T_{ijk} ; with i, j, k, l, m being the indices for batch, condition, time (in months), assay run and replicate respectively,
- A = Process mean at time zero,
- α_i = Random batch term at time zero; $\alpha_i \sim N(0, \sigma_\alpha^2)$,
- D_j = Condition specific term representing additional loss in early phase; d_{ij} = Random batch term (batch & condition specific) for additional loss at early phase; $d_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma_d^2)$.

The drop is only estimated for 5°C Inverted as determined by the indicator variables:

- Ind_{5C-Inv} is an indicator variable for condition 5°C Inverted vial orientation.
- $Ind_{1.5}$ is an indicator variable taking value 0 for measurements at time zero and 1 for all measurements above time zero. The subscript in $Ind_{1.5}$ indicates the second timepoint for condition 5°C Inverted vial orientation which is 1.5 months. Early phase is defined as the period between time zero and 1.5 months. $Ind_{1.5}$ ensures that the slope for condition 5°C Inverted vial orientation is estimated with measurements from the second time point onwards (i.e., excluding time zero measurements), where no additional loss due to adsorption is expected. This allows the estimation of the additional loss in early phase, which is the extra loss in potency above the loss per unit time (linear slope) due to temperature.
- β_j = Fixed condition specific slope,
- b_{ij} = Random batch slope component (batch & condition specific); $b_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma_b^2)$,
- W = Fixed quadratic term for condition 25°C Up,
- ω_i = Random batch specific quadratic term for condition 25°C Up; $\omega_i \sim N(0, \sigma_\omega^2)$,
- Ind_{25C-up} is an indicator variable for condition 25°C Up,
- $\gamma_{l(ik)}$ = Random assay run term; $\gamma_{l(ik)} \sim N(0, \sigma_\gamma^2)$, and
- $\varepsilon_{m(ijkl)}$ = Random residual error term for each observation; $\varepsilon_{m(ijkl)} \sim N(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2)$.

Intercept: It is worth noting that for each batch, since the studies for the five storage conditions are started at the same time, we estimate a single intercept per batch at time zero that is common to the five storage conditions.

One-state vs two-state kinetics: In the model above, the indicator variable Ind_{5C-Inv} ensures that the terms D_j and d_{ij} for additional loss in early phase are only estimated for condition 5°C inverted vial orientation. If these two terms are dropped from the model, 5°C Inverted vial orientation data will also be described by a simple linear relationship between potency and time. We refer to the

model including the term $(D_j + d_{ij}) \times Ind_{5C-Inv} * Ind_{1.5}$ as two-states kinetic model and the model without it as one-state kinetic model.

Quadratic term: Similarly, indicator variable Ind_{25C-up} ensures that the quadratic terms W and ω_i are only estimated for condition 25°C. For clarity, we note here that reference to one-state versus two-state kinetics models is only with respect to condition 5°C Inverted vial orientation. The quadratic term for condition 25°C is fitted for both the one-state and two-state kinetics models defined above.

The model parameters were estimated with SAS (Version 9.4, M6) using PROC MIXED with the PRIOR statement to produce posterior parameter estimates. The posterior distribution of shelf life, denoted as $T_{SL(j)}(r)$ for condition j , was calculated directly from the posterior parameter estimates as a derived variable for each posterior draw as follows:

- $T_{SL(j)}(r) = \frac{LS_{limit} - [A(r) + \alpha(r)]}{[\beta_j(r) + b(r)]}$ for conditions -60°C, -20°C and 5°C upright vial orientation,
 - $T_{SL(j)}(r) = \frac{LS_{limit} - [A(r) + \alpha(r) + D_j(r) + d(r)]}{[\beta_j(r) + b(r)]}$ for condition 5°C inverted vial orientation,
- and
- For condition 25°C, posterior distribution of $T_{SL(j)}(r)$ is obtained by solving for $T_{SL(j)}(r)$ in the following equation:
 - $LS_{limit} = [A(r) + \alpha(r)] + T_{SL(j)}(r) * [\beta_j(r) + b(r)] + T_{SL(j)}^2(r) * [W(r) + \omega(r)]$.

Where LS_{limit} is the end-of shelf-life specification limit; $A(r)$, $\beta_j(r)$, $D_j(r)$, $W(r)$ are the r^{th} draws of the posterior distribution of parameter A , β_j , D_j and W respectively; $\alpha(r)$, $d(r)$, $b(r)$, and $\omega(r)$ are random batch components simulated from a normal distribution with mean 0 and standard deviations corresponding to the r^{th} draw of the respective posterior distribution of variance parameters for α_i , d_{ij} , b_{ij} and ω_i (i.e., σ_α^2 , σ_d^2 , σ_b^2 and σ_ω^2).

Based on the derived posterior distributions of batch mean shelf-lives, the shelf-life claim for condition j is chosen as the 5th percentile value of $T_{SL(j)}(r)$. This is consistent with the definition of shelf life given in ICHQ1E, but modified to represent the distribution of batches, rather than processes. See Chow, 2007 for a general introduction and Altan et al., 2023 for additional details on a Bayesian approach.

In Figure 2 below, a graphical presentation of the two model fits is presented for a single batch as an illustration. We observe the following:

- In both models, the fitted profiles for each storage condition start at the same point at time zero as per the study design. A straight-line relationship is fitted for conditions conditions -60°C, -20°C and 5°C upright vial orientation. Further, the quadratic term for condition 25°C appears to capture the slightly non-linear nature of the relationship between assay measurements over time.
- For condition 5°C Inverted vial orientation, a straight-line relationship is fitted for the the one-state kinetic model. However, for the two-state kinetic model, there are two phases of potency loss. The first phase has a steeper drop in potency which is a combination of the initial drop in potency associated with vial inversion as explained above and normal potency loss over time due to exposure to the temperature condition. In the second phase, only the normal potency loss over time due to exposure to the temperature condition is present. A more detailed illustration of the two models focusing on condition 5°C Inverted vial orientation is presented graphically in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Graphical presentation of model fits (one vs two-state) for a single batch depicting the fitted profiles for the five storage conditions. The assay measurements are presented in asterisks (note that in this graph the run means at each time-point per storage condition are presented instead of the 9 individual measurements). The solid lines represent the model fit for each condition.

Figure 3: Graph of one-state versus two state kinetics models for condition 5°C with inverted vial orientation. For the two-state kinetics model, the first storage phase has two mechanisms of degradation, the extra loss, and the linear slope. The linear slope is the same one present in the second phase and is only estimated using data from the second phase.

Shelf-life: Finally, we compare the shelf-lives for condition 5°C with inverted vial orientation estimated from the two models for a single batch in Figure 4 below. Scientifically, the potency was expected to experience an initial drop, followed by a relatively constant potency over time for 5°C inverted vial orientation condition. The two-state model considers this scientific knowledge removing bias in the estimation of shelf-life by reducing misspecification. Consequently, the two-state model resulted in a longer shelf-life because it better described the nature of the stability profile for this condition.

Figure 4: Graphical comparison of derived shelf-life between one-state and two-state model for a single batch for condition 5°C with inverted vial orientation.

4. Summary

A segmented regression approach, within a mixed model framework, was proposed as a general method to characterize the stability profiles of a vaccine product. Compared to small molecule drug products, whose stability profiles tend to be well approximated by a zero-order kinetic model, vaccines can display departures from the simple zero order assumption. For example, a rapid initial loss and curvature can occur in some cases, and a model accommodating these divergent profiles is needed. The proposed model provides both flexibility in describing the divergent profiles, as well as variance component sources due to manufacturing variability, as well as analytical measurement uncertainty. The proposed model was found to perform well and justified through an AICc comparison. The final model was fitted in the Bayesian framework and the shelf-lives calculated as the intersection of the lower one-sided 95% confidence bound with a lower specification bound defining the lower limit of quality.

5. References

1. International Conference on Harmonization. ICH Q1E Guidance. Evaluation of Stability Data, Step 5. August 2003.
2. T.L. Schofield, Vaccine stability study design and analysis to support product licensure. *Biologicals* 2009. 37: 387–396.
3. Altan, S., Faya, P., Rauk, A., LeBlond, D., Seaman, J.W., Banton, D. Stability analysis using mixed models: a critique of tolerance interval methods and a probabilistic solution. *Pharm Stat.* 2023; 22(5): 784-796. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pst.2305>
4. Chow, S.-C. *Statistical design and analysis of stability studies*. Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2007. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781584889069>